

OPTIMIZATION AND EXPERIMENT OF COMPOSITE SQUARE BEAM

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to design a composite box beam in three-point bending with a high ratio of load-bearing/weight. First of all, a three-point bending experiments was conducted to the manufactured composite box beam and it was found the top of the box broken for exceeding the compressive stress limitation. Then, a finite element model the same as the experimental (original) parameter was established; comparing the analysis results with experimental data, they were in good agreement. Then, a basic shape of the square beam was got by using topological optimization of ANSYS. ANSYS APDL was used to model a parametric composite square beam, which can perform the geometric optimization of the square beam. The result shows that increase the height of the square beam's arch and the thickness of the top of the square beam within a certain range helps to reduce the maximum stress and increase the load apply on the square beam. Finally, the second composite square beam, which is almost the same as optimized result, was manufactured. An experiment was conducted to the second beam. The experiment results show: the square beam with optimized parameter has a better mechanical performance (the ratio of load-bearing/weight is 55.99N/g) than the square beam with initial parameter (the ratio of load-bearing/weight is 49.01N/g).

1 Introduction

The composite material is composed by two or more materials with differing properties [1]. The performance of composite is often better than their component, that's why we prefer composite. In this paper, we focus on fiber-reinforced composites, which composed of fibers embedded in a matrix [2]. Furthermore, laminated composite made of fiber

cloth is what this paper concern about. Composite material is a new kind of material, which has a lot of advantage, such as lightweight, high-strength, anti-fatigue and designable.

Box beam structure has high bending and torsional stiffness; additional, its overall performance is prominent and has reasonable force distribution. Box beams are widely used in civilian and military for its prominent structure performance. It can overcome the weakness of low stiffness of composites in some degree by using box beam structure and make full use of its advantage of high strength [3].

In 1957, Goldberg [4] proposes the theory of prismatic folded plate structures, in which discrete box beam into a number of rectangular plates, then, establishing equations and calculating by the basement of elastic plane stress theory and plate bending theory and utilizing the deformation and statics conditions of each combination. Vlasov [5] is a pioneer of the theoretical research of thin-walled closed cross section structure composed of isotropic material; he established the theory of thin walled beams in 1961.

The theoretical analysis is the basis of the actual structural stress analysis, but for many complex components, purely theoretical analysis is very difficult or even impossible to carry out. With the development of computer technology, numerical analysis methods can efficiently and accurately analyze the practical engineering structures of complex shape. In 2000, X.Xiangdong [6] utilized software he written based on plastic node method and general nonlinear finite element simulation method performs a simulation of box-beam hull model, and a result consistent with test was got; analytical calculation method to estimate the ultimate strength of box beam hull structure was proposed based on experiment and theoretical analysis. In 2007, S.Chang [7] analysis the reliability

of the box beam by utilizing Newman series expansion Monte Carlo simulation, and established a calculation model of thin-walled box beam considered material parameters with uncertainty. In 2013, Giovanni Belingardi performed a geometry optimization numerical simulation; a composite geometry size was got [8], which has the same impact effect with steel.

2 Theoretical Foundations

2.1 Stress-Strain Relationships

The stress is related to the strains by [9]:

$$\{\sigma\} = [D] \{\varepsilon^{el}\} \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\{\sigma\} = \text{stress vector} = [\sigma_x \ \sigma_y \ \sigma_z \ \sigma_{xy} \ \sigma_{yz} \ \sigma_{zx}]^T$$

[D] = elasticity or elastic stiffness matrix or stress-strain matrix.

$\{\varepsilon^{el}\} = \{\varepsilon\} - \{\varepsilon^{th}\}$ = elastic strain vector.

$\{\varepsilon^{th}\}$ = thermal strain vector.

$\{\varepsilon^{el}\}$ are the strains that cause stresses.

The shear strains (ε_{xy} , ε_{yz} , and ε_{xz}) are the engineering shear strains, which are twice the tensor shear strains. The ε notation is commonly used for tensor shear strains, but is used here as engineering shear strains for simplicity of output.

The stress vector is shown in the figure below. The sign convention for direct stresses and strains used throughout the ANSYS program is that tension is positive and compression is negative. For shears, positive is when the two applicable positive axes rotate toward each other.

Fig.1. Stress Vector Definition

Equation (1) may also be inverted to:

$$\{\varepsilon\} = [\varepsilon^{th}] + [D]^{-1} \{\sigma\} \quad (2)$$

For the 3-D case, the thermal strain vector is:

$$\{\varepsilon^{th}\} = \Delta T [\alpha_x^{se} \ \alpha_y^{se} \ \alpha_z^{se} \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T \quad (3)$$

where:

α_x^{se} = secant coefficient of thermal expansion in the x direction.

$$\Delta T = T - T_{ref}$$

T = current temperature at the point in question;

T_{ref} = reference (strain-free) temperature.

The flexibility or compliance matrix, $[D]^{-1}$ is:

$$[D]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_x & -\nu_{xy}/E_x & -\nu_{xz}/E_x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{yx}/E_y & 1/E_y & -\nu_{yz}/E_y & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\nu_{zx}/E_z & -\nu_{zy}/E_z & 1/E_z & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{xy} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{yz} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1/G_{xz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where typical terms are:

E_x = Young's modulus in the x direction ;

ν_{xy} = major Poisson's ratio;

ν_{yx} = minor Poisson's ratio;

G_{xy} = shear modulus in the xy plane.

Also, the $[D]^{-1}$ matrix is presumed to be symmetric, so that:

$$\frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_y} = \frac{\nu_{xy}}{E_x} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\nu_{zx}}{E_z} = \frac{\nu_{xz}}{E_x} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\nu_{zy}}{E_z} = \frac{\nu_{yz}}{E_y} \quad (7)$$

Because of the above three relationships, ν_{xy} , ν_{yz} , ν_{xz} , ν_{yx} , ν_{zy} , and ν_{zx} are not independent quantities and therefore the user should input either ν_{xy} , ν_{yz} , and ν_{xz} (input as PRXY, PRYZ, and PRXZ), or ν_{yx} , ν_{zy} , and ν_{zx} (input as NUXY, NUZY, and NUXZ). The use of Poisson's ratios for orthotropic materials sometimes causes confusion, so that care should be taken in their use. Assuming that E_x is larger than E_y , ν_{xy} (PRXY) is larger than ν_{yx} (NUXY). Hence, ν_{xy} is commonly referred to as the "major Poisson's ratio", because it is larger than ν_{yx} , which is commonly referred to as the "minor" Poisson's ratio. For orthotropic materials, the user needs to inquire of the source of the material property data as to which type

of input is appropriate. In practice, orthotropic material data are most often supplied in the major (PR-notation) form. For isotropic materials ($E_x = E_y = E_z$ and $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yz} = \nu_{xz}$), so it makes no difference which type of input is used.

Expanding equation (2) with equation (3) thru equation (7) and writing out the six equations explicitly,

$$\varepsilon_x = \alpha_x \Delta T + \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} - \frac{\nu_{xy} \sigma_y}{E_x} - \frac{\nu_{xz} \sigma_z}{E_x} \quad (8)$$

$$\varepsilon_y = \alpha_y \Delta T - \frac{\nu_{xy} \sigma_x}{E_x} + \frac{\sigma_y}{E_y} - \frac{\nu_{yz} \sigma_z}{E_y} \quad (9)$$

$$\varepsilon_z = \alpha_z \Delta T - \frac{\nu_{xz} \sigma_x}{E_x} - \frac{\nu_{yz} \sigma_y}{E_y} + \frac{\sigma_z}{E_z} \quad (10)$$

$$\varepsilon_{xy} = \frac{\sigma_{xy}}{G_{xy}} \quad (11)$$

$$\varepsilon_{yz} = \frac{\sigma_{yz}}{G_{yz}} \quad (12)$$

$$\varepsilon_{xz} = \frac{\sigma_{xz}}{G_{xz}} \quad (13)$$

where typical terms are:

ε_x = direct strain in the x direction;

σ_x = direct stress in the x direction;

ε_{xy} = shear strain in the x-y plane;

σ_{xy} = shear stress on the x-y plane.

Alternatively, Equation (1) may be expanded by first inverting equation (4) and then combining that result with equation (3) and equation (5) thru equation (7) to give six explicit equations:

$$\sigma_x = \frac{E_x}{h} \left(1 - (\nu_{yz})^2 \frac{E_z}{E_y} \right) (\varepsilon_x - \alpha_x \Delta T) + \frac{E_y}{h} \left(\nu_{xy} + \nu_{xz} \nu_{yz} \frac{E_z}{E_y} \right) (\varepsilon_y - \alpha_y \Delta T) + \frac{E_z}{h} (\nu_{xz} + \nu_{yz} \nu_{xy}) (\varepsilon_z - \alpha_z \Delta T) \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_y = \frac{E_y}{h} \left(\nu_{xy} + \nu_{xz} \nu_{yz} \frac{E_z}{E_y} \right) (\varepsilon_x - \alpha_x \Delta T) + \frac{E_y}{h} \left(1 - (\nu_{xz})^2 \frac{E_z}{E_x} \right) (\varepsilon_y - \alpha_y \Delta T) + \frac{E_z}{h} (\nu_{yz} + \nu_{xz} \nu_{xy}) (\varepsilon_z - \alpha_z \Delta T) \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_z = \frac{E_z}{h} (\nu_{xz} + \nu_{yz} \nu_{xy}) (\varepsilon_x - \alpha_x \Delta T) + \frac{E_z}{h} (\nu_{yz} + \nu_{xz} \nu_{xy}) (\varepsilon_y - \alpha_y \Delta T) + \frac{E_x}{h} \left(1 - (\nu_{xy})^2 \frac{E_y}{E_x} \right) (\varepsilon_z - \alpha_z \Delta T) \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = G_{xy} \varepsilon_{xy} \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_{yz} = G_{yz} \varepsilon_{yz} \quad (18)$$

$$\sigma_{xz} = G_{xz} \varepsilon_{xz} \quad (19)$$

where:

$$h = 1 - (\nu_{xy})^2 \frac{E_y}{E_x} - (\nu_{yz})^2 \frac{E_z}{E_y} - (\nu_{xz})^2 \frac{E_z}{E_x} - 2 \nu_{xy} \nu_{yz} \nu_{xz} \frac{E_z}{E_x} \quad (20)$$

The [D] matrix must be positive definite. The program checks each material property as used by each active element type to ensure that [D] is indeed positive definite. In the case of temperature dependent material properties, the evaluation is done at the uniform temperature (for the first load step). The material is always positive definite if the material is isotropic or if ν_{xy} , ν_{yz} , and ν_{xz} are all zero. When using the major Poisson's ratios (PRXY, PRYZ, PRXZ), h as defined in equation (20) must be positive for the material to be positive definite.

2.2 The Theory of Topological Optimization

The theory of topological optimization seeks to minimize or maximize the objective function (f) subject to the constraints (g_j) defined. The design variables (η_i) are internal, pseudodensities that are assigned to each finite element (i) in the topological problem. The pseudodensity for each element varies from 0 to 1; where $\eta_i \approx 0$ represents material to be removed; and $\eta_i \approx 1$ represents material that should be kept. Stated in simple mathematical terms, the optimization problem is as follows:

$$f = \text{a minimum/maximum w.r.t. } \eta_j \quad (21)$$

subject to

$$0 < \eta_j < 1 \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N) \quad (22)$$

$$\underline{g} < g_j < \bar{g} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M) \quad (23)$$

where:

N = number of elements;

M = number of constraints;

g_j = computed j th constraint value;

\underline{g} = lower bound for j th constraint;

\bar{g} = upper bound for j th constraint.

2.3 Theory of Design Optimization

The first order optimization method was used to analyze the composite square beam. This method of

optimization calculates and makes use of derivative information. Derivatives are formed for the objective function and the state variable penalty functions, leading to a search direction in design space. Various steepest descent and conjugate direction searches are performed during each iteration until convergence is reached. Each iteration is composed of subiterations that include search direction and gradient (i.e., derivatives) computations. In other words, one first order design optimization iteration will perform several analysis loops. Compared to the subproblem approximation method, this method is usually seen to be more computationally demanding and more accurate.

An unconstrained version of the problem is formulated as follows.

$$Q(x,q) = \frac{f}{f_0} + \sum_{i=1}^n P_x(x_i) + q \left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_1} P_g(g_i) + \sum_{i=1}^{m_2} P_h(h_i) + \sum_{i=1}^{m_3} P_w(w_i) \right) \quad (24)$$

where:

Q = dimensionless, unconstrained objective function;

$P_x, P_g, P_h,$ and P_w = penalties applied to the constrained design and state variables;

f_0 = reference objective function value that is selected from the current group of design sets.

Constraint satisfaction is controlled by a response surface parameter, q .

Exterior penalty functions (P_x) are applied to the design variables. State variable constraints are represented by extended-interior penalty functions (P_g, P_h, P_w).

The functions used for the remaining penalties are of a similar form.

As search directions are devised (see below), a certain computational advantage can be gained if the function Q is rewritten as the sum of two functions. Defining

$$Q_f(x) = \frac{f}{f_0} \quad (25)$$

and

$$Q_p(x,q) = \sum_{i=1}^n P_x(x_i) + q \left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_1} P_g(g_i) + \sum_{i=1}^{m_2} P_h(h_i) + \sum_{i=1}^{m_3} P_w(w_i) \right) \quad (26)$$

then equation (24) takes the form

$$Q(x,q) = Q_f(x) + Q_p(x,q) \quad (27)$$

The functions Q_f and Q_p relate to the objective function and the penalty constraints, respectively.

For each optimization iteration (j) a search direction vector, $\mathbf{d}^{(j)}$, is devised. The next iteration ($j+1$) is obtained from the following equation.

$$\mathbf{x}^{(j+1)} = \mathbf{x}^{(j)} + s_j \mathbf{d}^{(j)} \quad (28)$$

Measured from $\mathbf{x}^{(j)}$, the line search parameter, s_j , corresponds to the minimum value of Q in the direction $\mathbf{d}^{(j)}$. The solution for s_j uses a combination of a golden-section algorithm and a local quadratic fitting technique. The range of s_j is limited to

$$0 \leq s_j \leq \frac{S_{\max}}{100} s_j^* \quad (29)$$

where:

s_j^* = largest possible step size for the line search of the current iteration (internally computed) ;

S_{\max} = maximum (percent) line search step size.

The key to the solution of the global minimization of equation (27) relies on the sequential generation of the search directions and on internal adjustments of the response surface parameter (q). For the initial iteration ($j = 0$), the search direction is assumed to be the negative of the gradient of the unconstrained objective function.

$$\mathbf{d}^{(0)} = -\nabla Q_f(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}, q) = \mathbf{d}_f^{(0)} + \mathbf{d}_p^{(0)} \quad (30)$$

in which $q = 1$, and

$$\mathbf{d}_f^{(0)} = -\nabla Q_f(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{d}_p^{(0)} = -\nabla Q_p(\mathbf{x}^{(0)}) \quad (31)$$

Clearly for the initial iteration the search method is that of steepest descent. For subsequent iterations ($j > 0$), conjugate directions are formed according to the Polak-Ribiere recursion formula.

$$d^{(i)} = -\nabla Q(x^{(i)}, q_k) + r_{j-1} d^{(j-1)} \quad (32)$$

$$r_{j-1} = \frac{[\nabla Q(x^{(j)}, q) - \nabla Q(x^{(j-1)}, q)]^T \nabla Q(x^{(j)}, q)}{|\nabla Q(x^{(j-1)}, q)|^2} \quad (33)$$

Notice that when all design variable constraints are satisfied $P_x(x_i) = 0$. This means that q can be factored out of Q_p , and can be written as

$$Q_p(x^{(j)}, q) = q Q_p(x^{(j)}) \text{ if } \underline{x}_i \leq x_i \leq \bar{x}_i \quad (i=1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \quad (34)$$

If suitable corrections are made, q can be changed from iteration to iteration without destroying the conjugate nature of equation (32). Adjusting q provides internal control of state variable constraints, to push constraints to their limit values as necessary, as convergence is achieved. The justification for this becomes more evident once equation (32) is separated into two direction vectors:

$$d^{(j)} = d_f^{(j)} + d_p^{(j)} \quad (35)$$

where each direction has a separate recursion relationship,

$$d_f^{(j)} = -\nabla Q_f(x^{(j)}) + r_{j-1} d_f^{(j-1)} \quad (36)$$

$$d_p^{(j)} = -q \nabla Q_p(x^{(j)}) + r_{j-1} d_p^{(j-1)} \quad (37)$$

The algorithm is occasionally restarted by setting $r_{j-1} = 0$, forcing a steepest decent iteration. Restarting is employed whenever ill-conditioning is detected, convergence is nearly achieved, or constraint satisfaction of critical state variables is too conservative.

So far it has been assumed that the gradient vector is available. The gradient vector is computed using an approximation as follows:

$$\frac{\partial Q(x^{(j)})}{\partial x_i} \approx \frac{Q(x^{(j)} + \Delta x_i e) - Q(x^{(j)})}{\Delta x_i} \quad (38)$$

where:

e = vector with 1 in its i th component and 0 for all other components.

$$\Delta x_i = \frac{\Delta D}{100} (\bar{x}_i - \underline{x}_i)$$

ΔD = forward difference (in percent) step size.

First order iterations continue until either convergence is achieved or termination occurs. These two events are checked at the end of each optimization iteration.

Convergence is assumed when comparing the current iteration design set (j) to the previous ($j-1$) set and the best (b) set.

$$|f^{(j)} - f^{(j-1)}| \leq \tau \quad (39)$$

and

$$|f^{(j)} - f^b| \leq \tau \quad (40)$$

where:

τ = objective function tolerance

It is also a requirement that the final iteration used a steepest descent search. Otherwise, additional iterations are performed. In other words, a steepest descent iteration is forced and convergence rechecked.

Termination will occur when

$$n_i = N_i \quad (41)$$

where:

n_i = number of iterations;

N_i = allowed number of iterations.

3 Experiments before Optimization

An experiment was conducted before the optimization. We can get some important data of the material used in the beam from the experiment, such as stiffness and strength.

The test load and the bridge's basic shape is shown below. It's a typical shape of I beam in the figure below, but the composite beam we made is an arch square beam.

Fig. 2. The test form of the square beam

The perspective view of the square beam, which we are going to design, is shown below in fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Perspective view of the square beam

From the fig. 4, it's clearly that there is a reinforcement of each side of the beam and the middle of it. The reinforcement can guarantee much more property distribution of the weight. The geometric size is shown in below figure.

Fig. 4. Cross-sectional size

The length of the beam is 620mm (a little longer than 23 inch), the reinforcement length of the middle of the beam is 160mm and the reinforcement of the beam's sides is 40mm. There are much more parameters, which is design varies, are shown in below table.

Table. 1. The initial date of the square beam

The height of each side	25mm
The height of arch	35mm

The thickness of bottom	1.6mm
The thickness of webs	2.5mm
The thickness of top	2.2mm
The thickness of reinforcement	2mm

The initial date was made into an actual composite square beam, which is tested in the load instrument and the broken beam is shown below.

Fig. 5. The broken composite square beam

Fig. 6. The broken place

Fig. 7. The load-position curve of square beam

The weight of the square beam is 561g and the load curve of three-point bending test is shown above.

Table. 2. The ratio of load/weight of the initial beam

The weight of the beam	561g
The maximum load of the beam	27493N
The ratio of load/weight	49.01N/g

The composite of the beam is treated as isotropic in its stiffness, and the Young modulus of this material (carbon fiber) is given 46Gpa. The square beam's simulation was performed in the FEA software ANSYS, the displacement of which is close to the test above.

Fig. 8. The displacement of the beam in simulation

The maximum compress stress of the beam is 395MPa and the maximum tensile stress of the beam is 385MPa. From fig. 6, we can get the cause of the beam's broken is the compress of up of the beam exceed its limitation. However, the tensile strength of the carbon composite is much bigger than the compress strength; there is some kind of unreasonable for the tensile stress is smaller than the compress stress, which means there is long way to go to optimize the composite square beam.

4 Optimal Design of Square BEAM

4.1 Topological Optimization

The goal of topological optimization is get a basic shape of the beam, which we wish to provide a proper shape with light weight to carry more loads. Both the 2-D and 3-D topological optimization has been accomplished to obtain the best distribution of the materials, the element types been used in the optimization are PLANE82 and SOLID95 of ANASYS. The tendency of the weight distribution was used to strengthen on the beam.

Fig. 9. Density distribution (80% mass removed)

4.2 Geometric Optimization

An optimal design was perform utilizing the APDL of ANSYS and the stress limit as the state variables; the arch height and the thickness as the design variables; the quality of the square beam as the objective function to optimize the design.

Fig. 10. The heights vary with iterations

From fig. 10, we can get: for getting a high ratio of loads/weight in three-point bending test, we might decrease the height of each side but the height of arch can be a little higher.

Fig. 11. The thicknesses vary with iterations

From the fig above, adding the thickness of the top and decrease the thickness of the webs can improve the ratio the loads/weight in three-point bending test.

In the end, a composite square beam was made with the result date of optimal design, which is listed below.

Table. 3. The optimized parameters of square beam

The height of mouth	20mm
The height of arch	40mm
The thickness of bottom	2mm
The thickness of webs	2.5mm
The thickness of top	4mm
The thickness of reinforcement	2mm

The optimal design square beam was tested and the broken form is shown as below.

Fig. 12. The tested square beam

Table. 4. The ratio of load/weight of the optimized beam

The weight of the beam	697g
The maximum load of the beam	39002N
The ratio of load/weight	55.99N/g

The square beam was broken under the load of 8769lbf, which means 39022N and better than the initial one.

5 Conclusions

Topological optimization can help us confirm a basic shape and then geometric optimization can finally determine the exact shape of the structure. In the square beam with three-point bending test, the thickness of the bottom is not far-off the thickness of the webs of the square beam, which has reinforcements in the middle and the side of it. However, the thickness of the top is beyond twice of the bottom. It's not complicated to explain, for a square beam with three-point bending load, that the

top of the beam is mainly bearing a stress of compress and the bottom of the beam is mainly bearing stress of extrude. (A real composite unidirectional plate always has a extrude strength twice bigger than the compress strength of it). In some fixed load condition, the stiffness of composite made of fiber cloth can be treated as isotropic material. However, the compress strength of composite is much lower than its tensile, which mean there need more material if the component bear compress stress only.

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References

- [1] S. Guanlin and H. Gengkai "Mechanics of Composite Materials". 1st edition, Tsinghua University Press, 2006.
- [2] S. SPRINGER "Mechanics of Composite structures ". 1st edition, Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [3] Z. Lei "The Design and Static Analysis of Composite Box Girder Bridge Section", National Defense Science and Technology University, 2011
- [4] Goldberg J . Theory of prismatic folded plate structures . International Assoc. for Bridge and Structural Engineering Publications. 1957 (17) : 59-86.
- [5] Vlasov VZ . Thin-walled elastic beams . Jerusalem, Israel : Israel Program for Scientific Translation; 1961 .
- [6] X. Xiangdong. "An Experimental and Theoretical Study on Ultimate Strength of a Box Girder". Journal of Ship Mechanics, Vol. 4, No. 5. pp36-43, 2000
- [7] S.Chang. "Numerical simulation techniques for structural reliability analysis of box girders". Journal of Railway Science and Engineering, Vol. 4, No. 6, pp25-29, 2007
- [8] Giovanni Belingardi, Alem Tekalign Beyene. "Geometrical optimization of bumper beam profile made of pultruded composite by numerical simulation". Composite Structures 103(2013) 217-225. 2013.
- [9] Theory reference for ANSYS.